

THE EFFECTS OF ATMOSPHERIC MIS-ESTIMATION ON HYPERSPECTRAL-BASED ADAPTIVE MATCHED FILTER TARGET DETECTION AS MEASURED BY THE BHATTACHARYYA COEFFICIENT

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ABSTRACT

Accurate target detection and classification of hyperspectral imagery require that the measurement by the imager matches as closely as possible the known “true” target as collected under controlled conditions and stored in a classification database. Therefore, the effect of the radiation source and the atmosphere must be factored out of the result before detection is attempted. Our objective is to investigate the uncertainty in the detections due to the uncertainty in the estimation of atmospheric conditions. We apply a range of atmospheric profiles, correlated with relative humidity, to a MODTRAN-based prediction of the radiative transfer effect on simulated imagery using the Digital Imaging and Remote Sensing Image Generation Model. These profiles are taken from known distribution percentiles as obtained from historic meteorological measurements at the simulated site. We demonstrate the detection error, as measured by the Bhattacharyya coefficient, given the range of atmospheric conditions in the historic profile, and show that changes in the atmospheric assumptions change the values of the output for the adaptive matched filter.

Index Terms— hyperspectral imagery, adaptive matched filter, atmospheric uncertainty

1. INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric absorption of electromagnetic energy is a problem across the broader topic of remote sensing. Atmospheric scientists have spent a great deal of effort to characterize the atmosphere, estimate atmospheric parameters from data, and generate methodologies for removing those atmospheric effects (e.g., empirical line correction and MODTRAN [1], to name a few). Although many of the techniques for estimating atmospheric parameters and removing atmospheric effects from imagery have been very successful, there is a level of

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uncertainty in the estimates that are still unaccounted for on reconstructed data. Fig. 1 provides an example of how the sensor reaching radiance, reflected from a lambertian surface of zero emissivity, varies under three different atmospheric profiles drawn from the distributions over the Rome, NY area.

Fig. 1. Sensor reaching radiance for an ideal target (uniform 100% reflectance) over the visible wavelengths under atmospheric profiles corresponding to the 1st, 50th, and 99th percentile distributions by relative humidity.

This article provides a brief look at how the error in the estimate of the atmospheric affects the output of the adaptive matched filter (AMF) target detector in reconstructed hyperspectral images (i.e., image data converted from sensor-reaching radiance to estimated reflectance and analyzed in the illumination-neutral reflectance environment). We first apply distance measures between atmospheric profiles. This is a non-trivial problem and appears to have received little attention in the literature.

A good definition of a distance between two atmospheres

is a precursor to better understanding the effects of atmospheric estimation error on other processes. Example processes affected by atmospheric error include change detection, target detectors such as the AMF [2] or adaptive cosine estimator [2], and other algorithms such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) [3] used in vegetation health analysis.

The second aspect of this paper is to show how the input error manifests from a statistical point of view on the output of the target detector. The input error is defined as how far the estimated atmospheric profile is from the actual atmospheric conditions under which targets of interest are imaged. The output error is defined as the error as measured by the changes in the Bhattacharyya coefficient (BC) between the output target distributions of the AMF.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Distance Between Atmospheres

How are atmospheric profiles characterized? The most significant and widely recognized approach is to characterize the atmosphere by its water vapor content. Several measures of water vapor content exist: absolute humidity, water vapor mixing ratio, relative humidity, and others.

The values described vary as a function of altitude, which gives a good argument to consider an altitude-based distance measurement between the profiles themselves. We describe the distance between atmospheres as the Euclidean distance between the measures of water vapor mixing ratio w (in grams of H_2O per kilogram of all other gasses) at four radiosonde layers and eight different percentiles by relative humidity. There are other measures that may be of use: absolute humidity, for example, varies with pressure altitude. The water vapor mixing ratio-based distance is shown in Eqn. 1, where $z_i \in \{0m, 500m, 1000m, 1500m\}$, $\{a_1, a_2\}$ are the two atmospheric profiles being compared, and i is the current layer where $i = 1 \dots 4$. While radiosonde data often include other atmospheric parameters, water vapor mixing ratio is the most independent, and the other parameters yield much the same relationship. Results are presented in Section 4 using this methodology.

$$d_w(a_1, a_2) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^4 (w(a_1, z_i) - w(a_2, z_i))^2} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Adaptive Matched Filter

As described by Manolakis and Shaw [2], the AMF is a modified version of the log-likelihood ratio test (LLRT) that assumes the covariance matrix Σ is the same for both the target

and the background PDFs, $p_1(X)$ and $p_0(X)$:

$$\ln \Lambda(X) = \ln \frac{p_0(X)}{p_1(X)} = (\mu_1 - \mu_0)^T \cdot \Sigma^{-1} \cdot X \quad (2)$$

where X is the data (each sample a row vector) and μ_1 and μ_0 are the means of the probability density functions (column vectors) for the target and background, respectively.

In order to appropriately detect the presence of a target with spectral signature μ_0 amidst the image data X , we must first convert the sensor reaching radiances in X to reflectance by removing the effects of solar illumination under the estimated atmospheric conditions. However, because the exact atmospheric profile is unknown, and because our estimate of the profile carries with it an error of known distribution, we calculate the output of the AMF for image data simulated under a set of atmospheric profiles corresponding to known probability of occurrence. We thereby obtain sets of AMF outputs that can be compared to each other as described in Section 2.3.

2.3. Distance Between Distributions of the AMF Output

To simulate the images from which our target data is taken, we use the Digital Imaging and Remote Sensing Image Generation Model (DIRSIG) [4], a program developed by a team from Rochester Institute of Technology. This tool allows three-dimensional scene construction including the size, shape, and placement of objects in relation to other objects. It allows the simulation of a variety of imaging devices, platforms and mission profiles. Its output takes into consideration not only atmospheric conditions, location, and solar illumination, but adjacency effects and the Bidirectional Reflection Distribution Function (BRDF) effects of objects in the scene.

However, DIRSIG does not currently incorporate a sensor noise model into the data it generates, and they tend not to show the kind of probabilistic variation for which statistical tools such as the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) and area under the ROC curve (AUC) are well-suited unless scatterers are placed in the scene relative to targets of interest.

Our metric to evaluate the difference in AMF output (for target classes) under different atmospheric conditions is the BC. The BC measures the separation of two probability mass functions (PMFs) or normalized histograms, where the histogrammed values in this work are the 1-dimensional AMF output for each target class under a correct and misestimated set of atmospheric conditions. The BC is a reasonable approach as it has been shown that it does not make assumptions about the distribution of the PMF [5], a necessary requirement given the heavily mixed spectral distribution of a typical image. The BC is calculated by dividing the elements of each distribution into an arbitrary number of bins based on their values and then computing the formula:

$$BC = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{p_i \cdot q_i}$$

where p_i and q_i are the fraction of PMFs p and q that fall within the i th bin and n is the number of bins. Thus, the values for the coefficient should range between zero (for no overlap between the distributions) and one (for complete overlap). If there are N atmospheric profiles under consideration, then we need to generate $\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$ BCs between them.

The BC is sensitive to the choice of bin size: too large a bin will fail to detect differences between distributions, while too small a bin will fail to detect any similarity. We experimentally determine a bin size such that the BC shows variation based on the difference between profiles.

3. EXPERIMENTATION

The atmospheric profile data are acquired from the Laser Environmental Effects Distribution Reference (LEEDR) [6]. These data were collected from radiosonde measurements at multiple sites across the world. They are grouped by the month, time of day, and - most significantly - the percentile in which they fall in a distribution correlated to relative humidity. For the purposes of this paper, we consider atmospheric profiles taken at eight different percentiles of the distribution: 5%, 10%, 20%, 50%, 80%, 90%, 95%, and 99%.

The profiles taken at these distributions become user-defined atmospheres used by MODTRAN to generate the sensor-reaching radiance for targets with reflectance spectra as shown in Fig. 2(a). We use DIRSIG to simulate a single-capture data cube as collected from the AVIRIS platform. The image is rendered in three-color format in Fig. 2(b). The MODTRAN module of DIRSIG allows the images to be simulated using user-defined atmospheric profiles, by varying these profiles according to their distribution at the target location, we develop a set of images corresponding to those distributions. The scene geometry is of a sensor at an altitude of 3048m with a nadir zenith angle imaging a target on the surface at 300m MSL. The image is collected at 1:00 p.m. EDT on June 1, 2001 at a location of 43°E, 77°W.

After calculating the output of the AMF for a particular target as simulated under the eight atmospheric profiles, we then calculate the BC between the distributions of the AMF output.

4. RESULTS

The results of the comparison between the atmospheric profiles are shown in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3(a), we plot the BCs of the overlap between the AMF output of the six target panels for images generated under the 5th percentile of atmospheric profiles by relative humidity and the AMF output for images generated under the other seven atmospheric profiles. The BCs are plotted versus the Euclidean distance between the atmospheric profiles (Eqn. 1), where the x -axis is labeled with the corresponding percentile distribution from which the atmospheric profile was taken (vice the Euclidean distance

Fig. 2. (a) The reflectance spectra of the six colored panels used in the DIRSIG image. The caption reads as follows: white panel (light gray solid), gray panel (light gray dashed), black panel (dark gray dashed), red panel (medium gray dashed), green panel (medium gray solid), blue panel (dark gray solid). (b) The RGB representation of the simulated hyperspectral image of DIRSIG’s “Megascene” less simulated trees. The targets of interest are the six colored panels towards the bottom center of the image.

itself). This shows *relative* distance for each percentile compared to the *reference* profile.

In Fig. 3(a), we see that the value of the BC at the 5th percentile distribution is 1 for all targets; here we compare each AMF output against itself. In contrast, at the 20th percentile (corresponding to the Euclidean distance between the 5th and 20th percentiles), we see that the BC has fallen, in varying degrees, for all targets, indicating that the AMF output distributions have moved and no longer completely overlap. In Fig. 3(b) and Fig. 3(c), we use the AMF distributions from images generated under the 50th and 99th percentiles, respectively, as the baselines against which we compare the other percentiles.

As indicated by the inverse relationship between the BC and the Euclidean distance between atmospheric profiles, the output of the AMF tends to move away from its value at the baseline atmospheric profile as the profile changes; the more the profile changes, the greater the movement. Consistent with Fig. 1, where we note that the sensor reaching radiance for the 99th percentile is well separated from the others, while the 50th and 1st percentiles almost overlap, we observe from Fig. 3 that the Euclidean distances corresponding to the 5th, 10th, and 20th percentiles along the x -axis are relatively close together compared to the 90th, 95th, and 99th percentiles.

We further see varying sensitivities to profile changes depending on the material type. The AMF output corresponding to the detection of the red, black, gray, and white panels show substantial movement, as measured by the BC with changes in the estimated atmospheric parameters. On the other hand, the blue panel, and especially the green panel, are relatively insensitive to atmospheric mis-estimation. Our examination

of the data indicates that these sensitivity differences are a function of the targets' spectral position relative to other in-scene material classes and the change of the gradient of the linear discriminant functions created by the AMF; however, we do not yet propose any generalities.

Fig. 3. BCs between the (a) 5th, (b) 50th, and (c) 95th percentiles and all other percentiles as measured by Euclidean distance. Note that the while scale of the x-axis is Euclidean distance, the axis labels are the percentile distributions to which the Euclidean distances correspond. Note also that in figure (b), the data for the white and black panels are identical, and their respective graphs overlap completely.

5. CONCLUSION

The preceding analysis demonstrates AMF sensitivity to the estimate of atmospheric conditions. Future work will examine how this sensitivity translates into detection rates as measured by the ROC and AUC. Our preliminary examination suggests that, in contrast to the BC, which shows its highest value when the atmospheric parameters are exactly estimated, the AUC, in contrast, shows no such pattern, and in fact is much more dependent on material type.

In addition to incorporating a realistic sensor noise model, future work will make use of more robust images. Such images will include more realistic rendering of trees and grass, as well as texture maps that give greater variation to objects in the scene. Furthermore, we intend to explore target sets that are spectrally close together and far apart, as well as dominant in different portions of the spectrum. In this way, we will gain a better understanding of which target types are more sensitive to atmospheric mis-estimation and the extent to which similar AMF distributions move relative to each other.

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